

Experiential Marketing and the Transformation of Traditional Retailing

Samet AYDIN

Maltepe University

Faculty of Business and Management Sciences

Department of International Trade and Logistics

Istanbul, Turkey

sametaydin@maltepe.edu.tr

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2275-4682>

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Abstract

Traditional retailing has undergone a profound transformation driven by shifting consumer expectations, an increase in e-commerce, and growing demand for immersive shopping environments. Experiential marketing has emerged as a strategic approach aimed at creating memorable, multisensory, and emotionally engaging retail experiences. Rather than focusing solely on products and transactions, experiential retailing emphasizes sensory stimulation, emotional connection, aesthetic design, and interactive participation, which collectively influence customer satisfaction, engagement, and loyalty. Prior research highlights that hedonic and utilitarian motivations, environmental cues, and holistic experience design significantly shape consumer behavior within retail settings. This study synthesizes key theoretical perspectives on experiential marketing and examines their implications for the redesign of physical retail spaces. Experience-based strategies have become essential for retailers seeking differentiation and a sustained competitive advantage in an increasingly digital marketplace.

Keywords: Experiential marketing, Experiential retailing, Customer experience, Hedonic consumption, Sensory marketing, Retail design, Omni-channel retailing.

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Introduction

Retail, an indispensable element of commerce, has evolved into an industry that encompasses the management of processes combining human elements in terms of personnel and customers, real estate and property management, art-related elements such as fashion and design, and contemporary developments such as technology and information processing. The rapid growth of e-commerce, in line with the development of Internet technologies and consumers' adoption of online shopping, poses a significant threat to traditional retail. However, from the customer's perspective, shopping has gone beyond being an action that merely satisfies needs based on logic; it has become a complex activity that involves emotions and impulses. Unlike purchasing, shopping encompasses entertainment, self-expression, personal pleasure, and satisfaction to meet and serve customers' desires that go beyond their needs.

Purchasing, as is still the case in industrial markets, is generally based on rational decisions, whereas in consumer markets, it is observed that customers' impulses dominate shopping behavior (Morrison and Crane, 2007). Customer impulses are also sensitive to design elements in the shopping environment (e.g., presentation, color, lighting, and sound). Retailers, recognizing the impact of these impulses, seek to satisfy customers by complementing their needs for products and services with pleasure-related elements, or by emphasizing existing pleasure opportunities associated with the product/service. They strive to differentiate themselves from competitors by creating experiences that combine elements such as pleasure, excitement, and appreciation of their customers (Kim, 2001). Simultaneously, retailers aim to increase customers' purchase frequency or purchase volume with these pleasure elements.

For example, today's shopping malls have become lifestyle centers, offering not only stores that sell products but also units that meet customers' daily needs such as banks and/or ATMs, dry cleaners, hairdressers, shoe repair shops, etc., and entertainment facilities such as cinemas, children's playgrounds, bowling alleys, restaurants, cafeterias, and bistros for dining and drinking. Customers of all ages can enjoy themselves on their own or with groups of friends and families. The holistic experience created can translate into a synergistic effect and mutual benefits for all businesses within the shopping mall. As customers spend more time in space, they spend more money. Therefore, mall managers diversify and differentiate their experiences by organizing events, such as music, shows, activities, concerts, and dancing, to keep customers in the space longer.

A fun retail experience is crucial for creating a memorable experience for customers and converting this positive evaluation into sales (Groeppe and Bloch, 1990). Simply attracting customers to a store is not sufficient for success in retail. In a highly competitive sector such as retail, providing customers with a unique experience within the store has become increasingly important. The retail environment is no longer just a place where products are

sold; it has become a place where customers are provided with information and education, where customers are given the opportunity to try out products and gain experience in using them, where customers can have fun, enjoy themselves, and ultimately feel good about themselves. Therefore, details such as the decor, music, colors, and lighting chosen and used for retail environments are not sufficient on their own. Often, the aim is for these elements to create an experience through well-designed, holistic harmony, resulting in memories that will remain permanently in customers' minds. These memories then draw consumers back to these retail environments for future purchases. Pine and Gilmore (1998) also emphasized the transformation of customers' shopping trips into memorable experiences and argued that what retailers offer customers and what customers purchase is not a product or service, but rather an "experience."

In line with the above, experiential shopping can occur not only in extraordinary environments such as fairs and special events, but also in traditional retail environments that are part of the customer's daily life. The concept of shoppertainment refers precisely to this, namely, the combination of shopping and entertainment in a single location. Music performances, art shows, dance shows, events, etc., frequently held in shopping malls, aim to create an environment that supports shopping (Sherman et al., 1997). This approach is also evident for individual stores. For example, at the Apple Store, you can try out products as you wish. At D&R (a bookstore in Turkey), one can buy a book and read it on a chair. It is believed that when a comfortable environment is created, people will stay there longer and want to be part of it. However, limiting experience has also emerged as a strategy. For example, the BİM brand, which has spread discount retailing throughout Turkey, emphasizes simplicity to its customers, almost as if to say, "quickly buy cheap products and leave." BİM attributes its lack of special shelf arrangements, lighting, colorful decorations, and other elements found in other stores to its goal of creating a perception among customers that being cheap and staying cheap is secret.

This section addresses the experiential marketing approach, specifically in the retail context. First, general information about the approach is provided, followed by an examination of how experiences are created in the retail sector and what effects these experiences have on customer attitudes. After exploring the topic under the heading of experiential retail, the discussion will focus on what design elements physical stores should incorporate.

1. Experiential Marketing

Experiential marketing is a marketing approach, particularly in consumer markets where businesses create unforgettable, extraordinary experiences for customers encompassing all products and services, and relationships with customers are built around these experiences (Caru and Cova, 2007). The experiential marketing approach aims to make customer relationships unique and sustainable over the long term. In experiential marketing, an

interaction that strongly appeals to the emotions and senses of customers is established between the customer and the product or brand, thereby attempting to influence customers' purchasing preferences.

Today, destructive competition prevails and technology has found a wide place in every aspect of life and the importance of experiential marketing has reached its peak. This was first mentioned in the late 20th century in Pine and Gilmore's (1999) "The Experience Economy" and Schmitt's (1999) "Experiential Marketing." Although Pine and Gilmore's (1999) emphasis on experience is accurate, it is crucial that these experiences translate into an economic proposition that yields monetary value for customers and sustainable profits for businesses. This point is expressed by Kim and Sullivan (2007) as customers now expressing themselves through consumption rather than purchasing commoditized products and structuring their lives, preferences, and relationships through "consumption."

Traditional marketing strategies based on products and prices fail to provide long-term differentiation and competitive advantage. Instead, the focus should be on customers (Holbrook 2000). Beyond elements such as product quality, perceived prestige, and service variety, offering customers a unique experience has become an important marketing topic. Businesses strive to differentiate themselves in competition by creating experiences that resonate with their customers' emotions. Shopping follows the sequence of "see, touch, feel, and choose." Customer progression through these stages varies depending on the brand, product category, and other elements of the marketing mix (Holbrook and Hirschman, 1982).

These experiences, supported by emotions and senses, contribute to indicators such as customer satisfaction, loyalty, and new customer acquisition related to marketing performance, thereby demonstrating tangible effects on companies' market success. Experiential marketing goes beyond the products or services that consumers purchase, addressing consumption through an experimental approach.

In line with this understanding, in the era referred to as the "experience economy," it is becoming increasingly important to determine how to create and sustain experiences that will satisfy customers and enable them to express themselves. As experiences are formed subjectively based on individuals' past habits, tastes, perceptions, emotions, and other personality traits, it can be said that each consumer has unique experiences (Schmitt, 1999).

Experiential marketing involves marketing a product or service through experience; in this process, the customer becomes emotionally involved and connects with the elements designed to create the experience. A well-designed experience captures consumer attention and emotions (Hoch, 2002). Unlike traditional marketing, which focuses on ensuring customer satisfaction, the primary goal of experiential marketing is to create emotional loyalty among consumers (McCole, 2004).

According to Schmitt (1999), experiential marketing aims to make customers feel, think about, relate to, and act with companies and brands. Schmitt (2003) suggests that, from a marketing perspective, five different types of experiences can be created for customers. These are:

1. Sensory experience: The aspect of the experience that appeals to the senses, related to sight, hearing, smell, and touch.
2. Emotional experience: Internal feelings and emotions related to the experience environment.
3. Cognitive experience: What elements constitute the experience created in the customer's mind.
4. Behavioral experience: Experiences related to behaviors and lifestyles.
5. Relational experience: Previous experiences and belonging to a social group or culture and social recognition.

These five strategic experience models ensure the creation of a unique holistic experience for each customer.

1.1. Endless Consumption

It cannot be said that the common characteristic of customers at restaurants such as Burger King, Divan, and Günaydın, which are located very close to each other at Bağdat Avenue at any given time, is filling their stomachs. It is also possible that the same people could be customers of all of these restaurants at different times. However, when considering special occasions, such as a couple's first date, wedding anniversary, or birthday celebration, the choice of venue for dining will naturally change. Special decoration, perhaps a little prestigious but ultimately a comfortable environment, and a professional presentation accompanied by exquisite flavors can be a daily routine for one person, but for another, it can be an experience they want to enjoy on special occasions limited to a few times a year. Based on this example, the symbolic meanings of all elements related to consumption, as much as the things consumed, express the underlying meanings of consumers' consumption needs. As Baudrillard (1998) emphasizes, our consumption choices are changing to gain a place in society, shape how people think about us, and feel ourselves in a certain status. However, consumption can also occur in the opposite direction—toward cheaper, less ostentatious, and more modest choices—as a way of sending a message to society rather than simply pursuing more, more luxurious, and more expensive items. In conclusion, consumption, which occurs every day and every moment, is not limited to needs alone; it also provides significant clues about people's preferences, choices, and, ultimately, themselves.

Dholakia (1999) argues that in addition to satisfying consumers' needs for specific products, shopping also involves consumption aimed at socializing, obtaining benefits

(utilitarian), and deriving pleasure (hedonistic). Consumption aimed at socializing includes exploring the environment, mingling with people, and chatting with different individuals, such as salespeople or other customers. Utilitarian consumption involves customers seizing opportunities for cheap products that are periodically discounted or in excess stock, securing price advantages through bargaining, and enjoying the attention they receive as customers in the retail environment. Hedonic consumption, on the other hand, involves the customer achieving aesthetic satisfaction, satisfying their visual pleasure, observing product presentations under brightly colored decorations, and enjoying satisfying scents in food and cosmetics. Apart from these, shopping can be seen as a stroll or sometimes even a sport in the sense of walking for consumers. The more elements consumers find in a retail environment that appeal to these impulses that drive them to action, the more inclined they are to browse, spend more time, and ultimately make purchases, that is, pay money.

According to Hirschman and Holbrook (1982), hedonic consumption “refers to consumer behavior related to the sensory, fantasy, and emotional aspects of a person’s experience with products.” Hedonic shopping emphasizes concepts such as pleasure, excitement, and escape, whereas in utilitarian shopping, the path to satisfaction lies in completing the shopping task (Baker et al., 2002). This is because utilitarian shopping tends to have a more functional purpose than pleasure and enjoyment (Wertebroch and Dhar, 2000).

Today, customers want to be part of the experience and personalize it, going beyond simply accepting the experiences prepared for them in retail environments. Customers’ perception of the experience involves cognitively selecting, organizing, and interpreting what is offered to them. In this regard, retailers should focus on enabling customers to find something that appeals to them among hundreds of different attention-grabbing elements in a shopping environment, capture their attention, and then allow customers to organize the attention-grabbing elements provided to them in line with their own beliefs, values, and tastes and to store some of these subjective interpretations in their minds for later use.

1.2. Consumers and Their Emotions

Among the many factors influencing consumer purchasing behavior, emotions play a significant role, which is why this topic is receiving increasing attention from both academics and industry professionals. Beyond consumption behavior, a person’s emotional structure and current emotional state also influence human behavior. An individual’s emotions are influenced by their personality, temporary conditions related to the current situation, and environmental stimuli (Mehrabian and Russell, 1974). The characteristics that make up an individual’s personality shape both their emotions and their interactions with the environment, and they are also influenced by the environment. These emotions were expressed as pleasure, love, anger, empathy, and desire.

Emotions also influence consumer choices in retail environments. Therefore, emotions play an important role in consumers' shopping experiences (Mehrabian, 1997). Consumers' moods and emotional states can influence their decision to go shopping and their choice of store during their shopping trips. However, to translate into a purchase, they need to find stimuli in a store that matches their emotions, interpret them, and take action to make a purchase, or more accurately, be "prompted" to do so (Dawson et al., 1990).

1.3. Satisfying the Senses

These senses are important in experiential retailing because they enable customers to perceive the store in a way that creates their own unique coding of the store. Appealing to customers through the five senses—sight, smell, hearing, touch, and taste—leads to sensory engagement and shapes the customer's experience (Kim and Sullivan, 2007). There were also significant interactions between sensory perceptions and consumer emotions. Retail environments supported by as many senses as possible influence consumers to be stimulated in this way, obtain a unique experience, and take action towards purchasing (Senthil et al., 2012).

Consumers evaluate the retail environment and the products and services found there using adjectives such as pleasant, glamorous, sincere, fresh, and new, based on their sensory perceptions. The aromas associated with freshly cooked and prepared food and beverages are used not only in restaurants and cafeterias but also in environments such as cinemas and hypermarkets. Beyond this, unique scents that customers cannot find elsewhere are also used in stores to create memorable effects on consumers. Along with visual elements such as lights and colors, the rhythm and tone of music also serve to satisfy consumers' senses.

2. Experiential Retailing

In today's competitive environment, where e-commerce is widely embraced by customers and online retailing (e-retail) is becoming increasingly prevalent in many different areas, it is no longer sufficient for traditional retailers to simply put products on the shelf and wait for them to sell, thus guaranteeing failure in the long run. Competitive tools from previous eras, such as larger stores, a wider variety of products, flexible return policies, and long working hours, no longer hold meaning for consumers who have begun to live online.

In developed economies, sales efforts focus less on product and service offerings and more on developing consumers' emotional attachment to the product and its brand (Pine and Gilmore, 1999). Modern retail elements in these economies also strive to reach customers both physically and psychologically to avoid competition and differentiate themselves from their competitors in oligopolistic markets where the number of players has decreased,

but the level of competition has intensified. In this way, they choose to appeal to customers' hearts and minds, offering an experience consisting of unforgettable memories.

Experiential retailing is a strategy that transforms products, services, and presentations prepared for customers into holistic consumption experiences. (Kim et al., 2007). Consumption satisfies consumers' emotional and pleasure-seeking desires (hedonic) as well as their rational and functional (utilitarian) needs, allowing them to fulfill psychological needs, such as self-perception, self-expression, and feeling good about themselves as human beings (Kim et al., 2007). Experiential retail is an approach that combines technology, interactive features, and entertainment elements in carefully designed store environments, transforming the purchase of products and services into an enjoyable activity with competent staff in human relationships. This aims to steer consumers toward a "spend with pleasure" mindset rather than a "buy and leave" mentality through the consumption experience created for the customer (Holbrook et al., 1984).

In experiential retailing, businesses provide customers with an environment in which they often feel more free in sales-related activities and at the point of sale, believing that they are in control. The goal is for customers to form emotional bonds under their own control and guidance (Schmitt, 2003). Customers are also involved in designing the experiences that businesses want to create for them.

In experiential retailing, this is made possible by the careful design of the environmental elements of the retail setting. Through the experience created by paying close attention to customers and organizing elements in a sincere and trustworthy manner, the goal is for customers to interact directly with the brand's products and services, and through the relationship established, for the customer to perceive value and be motivated to make a purchase (Donovan et al., 1994).

In this context, Viaport Asia Outlet Shopping in Istanbul is an example that appeals to both the utilitarian and hedonic aspects of modern shopping centers. Viaport Asia Outlet Shopping, which began operating in 2008, is an important example and has become one of the most visited shopping centers in the country. With over 200 stores, entertainment centers, cinema, and facilities that meet all other needs, business has become the center of social life in the region, combining open-air architecture with a street concept. Although located on the side of a highway, it features dining areas with an artificial lake, a small zoo, an entertainment center, bowling and cinema, and a landscape decorated with flowers. Viaport Asia, with its Bedesten adorned with miniature architecture reminiscent of the Grand Bazaar, promises a rich shopping and entertainment experience, offering all colors of life to people of all ages and groups (Viaport, 2020).

2.1. Holistic Retail Experience

As previously mentioned, it has been argued that experiences elicit sensory, physical, cognitive, and emotional responses in consumers (Mossberg, 2007). Based on this, it is expected that major retail brands in the 21st century will promise consumers a holistic experience rather than just products and services. For example, brands such as Apple, recognizing the importance of the in-store experience, strive to develop a bond with the consumer groups that their products appeal to by offering an experience that goes beyond the conventional.

The Viaport example, which focuses on imagination, feelings, and entertainment, is also mentioned in Hirschmann and Holbrook's (1982) experiential purchasing model. Indeed, all these can be offered together in modern shopping malls. Consumers pay at shopping malls for the time they spend being happy in that environment.

Pine and Gilmore (1999) defined the elements that constitute the holistic retail experience as the "4Es of Retail," based on the initial letters of the corresponding English terms, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Holistic Retail Experience

Source: Pine and Gilmore (1999)

The four different experience dimensions— education, entertainment, aesthetics, and escapism—vary with the customer's active participation and involvement in the experience. The degree of participation is related to customer engagement (Fiore et al., 2007), and, as a result, an experience is inevitably created in all environments where the business or brand interacts with the customer.

2.1.1. Educational

This dimension combines education and entertainment. Retailers use this information in various ways. Examples include a hardware store's wood-painting workshop and IKEA's activities for children. Retailers do not just display products; they also provide examples of how the product can be used and incorporated into everyday life, even taking customers on a tour of that life, as IKEA does.

Ultimately, efforts such as discount days and return policies alone, as stores have done in the past, are no longer sufficient. By offering fun and educational activities, retailers can differentiate their shopping experiences. The aim is for consumers who learn and have fun forming a bond with the business and brand, thereby encouraging consumption. Today, retailers can offer educational content about their products and their uses to consumers not only in physical environments, but also online through platforms such as YouTube and Facebook.

2.1.2. Entertainment

Shopping can be likened to a show in which the customer is both a player and spectator, actively interacting with other people and objects by seeing and being seen. In today's competitive environment, many businesses have realized that they need to incorporate entertainment into their retail mix to attract customers (Sit and Birch, 2014).

Customers now seek products that bring pleasure and allow them to express their personalities and lifestyles. In this sense, the act of purchasing a product consists of emotional stimuli related to entertainment (Kim et al., 2007). Large retailers have now begun to allocate more space per square meter to entertainment and dining, which are key elements of experience in their interior designs. Customized colors, decorations, architecture, and sound elements were used for this purpose. For example, Isfanbul Theme Park, which opened in 2013, offers its consumers a unique shopping center architecture with storefronts that are all different from each other, shopping streets with a nostalgic tram passing through them, a roller coaster that reaches speeds of 110 kph, and more than 30 other units that offer adrenaline and excitement, all in a single location (Isfanbul, 2020).

As an example of a single retailer, Decathlon, founded in France in 1976 and opening its first store in Turkey in 2010, can be cited. The company is an international chain of stores that carries sports equipment from many different brands. Decathlon goes beyond simply selling products; it introduces consumers to different sports or hobbies in its stores, provides opportunities to try them out by setting up special play areas, and frequently organizes events in open spaces where more expert participants perform (Decathlon, 2020).

2.1.3. Aesthetics

When we think of a shopping street on the city's main thoroughfares, we imagine wide sidewalks, landscaping, people sitting in cafes, perhaps street musicians, smells coming from shops and bakeries, and a colorful, bustling environment. Sensory details, such as visual, auditory, and olfactory elements, should also be uniquely designed within the store. Thus, the store should also appeal to consumers' aesthetic tastes. The store's layout, decoration, lighting, and product placement attract customers' interest and attention (Bitner, 1992). Simultaneously, it reflects or creates the identity of the retailer's brand.

The design elements in a store influence customers' enjoyment and the amount of money they spend. Store windows play an important role. A design that invites people passing by a store on the street or in the mall to enter should be preferred. Generally, people do not like spending money. What actually makes them enjoy spending money is the pleasure they get from the place where they make their purchases.

Customers want to experience sensory pleasures, including psychological stimuli. Stimuli are transmitted to the brain via the senses combined in the brain to create unique coding in the consumer's mind associated with that environment. This code is unique because it is related to an individual's tastes, preferences, and even physiological characteristics. Elements such as eye-catching colors and movements (mechanical movement, falling water, and device operation) can be entertaining. These elements should be used to make physical environments more appealing, especially for audiences who spend a lot of time online. For example, the LEGOLAND Discovery Center in Istanbul offers children an experience consisting of color and design that cannot be found online, in addition to playing and learning (LEGO, 2020). Similarly, the Alaçatı Restaurants offer a decoration dominated by blue and white colors to give an Aegean breeze.

2.1.4. Escapism

Success in retail depends on offering customers a highly distinctive and memorable experience (Sachdeva and Goel, 2015). People tire of constantly being in the same environment or sometimes want to escape from their surroundings, which they achieve by going to a different escape environment. Sometimes, this is the forest, the seaside, parks, gardens, etc. For customers, shopping is often an escape from everyday issues (Babin et al., 1994). Apart from those who shop for utilitarian purposes, a significant customer group also considers the enjoyable aspects of shopping an accessible escape for themselves (Rook, 1987). Thus, customers who want to escape the chaos and stress of daily life want to escape their troubles and worries by feeling like they are in a different world.

Therefore, in retail, how things are sold often takes precedence over what is being sold. The future of retail also depends on how retailers change customers' emotions, feelings, and psychology (Sachdeva and Goel, 2015).

2.2. Experiential Retail Design

Pine and Gilmore (1998) proposed five fundamental principles of experience design, as shown in Figure 2. The first principle is to theme the experience and create a unique theme around it. This chosen theme forms the basis for the experience and facilitates customer perception. The second principle aligns customer perceptions with carefully selected positive cues presented to them. It involves finding and using specific cues to create and reinforce an experience. The third design principle, eliminating negative cues, involves completely removing any cues that conflict with, diminish, or distract the experience theme. The fourth principle, creating lasting memories, focuses on ensuring that customers remember these experiences even after a significant period. Finally, the fifth design element, integrating the five senses, encompasses the need for touch, hearing, taste, sight, and smell, and the responses to these (Pine and Gilmore, 1999).

Figure 2. Experience Design in Retail

Source: Pine and Gilmore (1999)

This model enables retailers to ensure that customers notice, perceive, evaluate, and accept the differences in their stores, while also supporting the formation of a store image that creates a bond between customers and the store (Pine and Gilmore, 1999).

2.2.1. Theming the Experience

There are many special days throughout the year, including holidays, celebrations, and commemorations. The theme and date of these special days often vary from country to country, such as October 29, Turkey. Some special days, such as Mother's Day and Valentine's Day, are celebrated simultaneously by billions of people across a wide geographical area worldwide. It is well known that consumers' shopping volumes are high on special days. Therefore, retailers are seen to redesign the design elements and displays in their stores based on their characteristics.

By drawing inspiration from shopping during special occasions or on the days leading up to them, one can also assign meaning to other so-called "non-special" days by introducing different themes. For example, a fashion retailer could design special weeks based on colors (blue or beige weeks, sports, dance days, etc.). On these special days, lighting, decoration, product displays, and even staff uniforms in the store could be redesigned to highlight the chosen color. The examples mentioned are also applied to hotels and restaurants in the form of Mexican days, Argentine weeks, etc. Similarly, a sports goods retailer can select days, such as famous athletes' birthdays, and highlight specific product groups on those days with visual elements. The possibilities here are limited to marketers' imaginations.

2.2.2. Designing Positive Cues

Products offered in retail are often tangible, whereas the services provided are abstract and subjective. The tangible features of a store often shape abstract perceptions. For example, when Apple Stores, which had been closed for a long time during the COVID-19 pandemic, reopened store staff wore N95 masks, which were difficult to find for a certain period. This seemingly simple detail results in consumers perceiving that the company values its employees, thus creating a positive impression of the brand.

Just as the receptionist creates the first impression of a hotel, customers should find clues from the moment they enter the store, which is consistent with what the brand promises and represents. Examples include the physical characteristics of employees, their attire, and the technological level of equipment used. (Bitner, 1992).

2.2.3. Eliminating Negative Cues

Designing positive impressions is as important as ensuring that all elements that can be perceived negatively are prevented. Anything that contradicts, diminishes, or distracts the customer from the experience theme can be considered a negative cue. This negative cue could be a dusty product, a tired and unmotivated employee, an empty shelf where the product should be, or a flickering light fixture.

Particularly in interactions with products and employees, cues that disappoint customers or surprise them in a negative way must be carefully and continuously monitored. This responsibility lies not only with the marketing department but also with all functions within the company. In the best-case scenario, negative cues result in customers avoiding purchases. If customers attach more meaning to these cues, it will lead to negative experiences shared by word-of-mouth or social media, causing even greater problems for businesses.

2.2.4. Making a Lasting Impression

If you were asked, “What are the five things you remember from your five years of elementary school?”, what would come to mind? This example is effective in showing how fleeting experiences are in terms of memory. In the retail environment, creating a lasting experience for customers may not occur with a single visit. Therefore, retailers should strive to reinforce their presence in customer memories by consistently and persistently offering unique experiences.

When offering experiences to customers, rich sensory and emotional experiences are important for positive and memorable experiences. However, the lasting impact of negative experiences and customer disappointment must also be considered. Both positive and negative experiences should be followed after purchase. It should be noted that communication and interaction with customers in this direction are reinforcing.

2.2.5. Integrating the Five Senses

The impact of the senses on creating customer experiences must be carefully considered, and holistic harmony between them must be ensured. Many mistakes are made when using these senses. For example, sales staff closely and persistently following customers around a store can sometimes have a negative effect on the customer’s perception. Customers should be given time and opportunity to touch and feel products. In this regard, store layouts should be carefully designed (Bezawada et al., 2009). In addition, the sales staff should receive awareness training.

Digital or printed visuals should be selected to create a lasting impact. A store may have its own unique scent, or different scents may be used in different areas. Of course, in a ready-to-wear retailer, the smell of food eaten by staff on the back would not be welcome. However, the sense of taste is not exclusive to restaurants. For example, IKEA adds a taste element to its customers’ furniture and home goods shopping experience by offering hot dogs and special flavors in a separate area after checkout. Regarding auditory features, attention should be paid not only to the selection of music and rhythm but also to the need to ensure and maintain silence. Ultimately, ensuring that all these senses align with the brand’s commitment to the consumer is one of the key tasks to pursue for ultimate success.

Conclusion

The rapid evolution of consumer expectations and continued expansion of e-commerce have reshaped the role and relevance of physical retail environments. This study shows that traditional retailing can no longer rely on product assortment, convenience, or price-based differentiation alone. Instead, the creation of memorable and meaningful experiences has become central in attracting, engaging, and retaining customers. Experiential marketing provides a theoretical and strategic framework through which retailers can design multisensory, emotionally rich, and interaction-driven environments that align with contemporary consumption patterns, characterized by hedonic, symbolic, and experiential motivations.

The discussion demonstrates that experiential retailing requires retailers to orchestrate sensory cues, emotional triggers, environmental design elements, and symbolic meanings in a coherent and holistic manner. Frameworks such as Schmitt's strategic experiential modules and Pine and Gilmore's 4Es highlight the multidimensional structure of customer experience—encompassing education, entertainment, aesthetics, and escapism—and illustrate how intentional experience design can create value beyond functional utility. The importance of eliminating negative cues, reinforcing positive impressions, and maintaining thematic consistency further underscores that experience creation is a strategic and operational endeavor.

Overall, the analysis indicates that the future of brick-and-mortar retailing depends on the ability of retailers to become experience curators, rather than mere product sellers. Experience-centered strategies not only enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty but also support differentiation in a marketplace where digital alternatives continue to expand. As technological integration deepens and consumer behaviors evolve, successful retailers will combine sensory design, emotional engagement, and interactive participation to deliver compelling, authentic, and memorable retail experiences. Future research may further investigate how emerging technologies such as augmented reality, artificial intelligence, and data-driven personalization can be integrated into experiential retailing to enhance customer engagement and strengthen competitive advantage.

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